

Impact of Electric cooking on Electricity Generation and Demand in Kenya

Mercy Kimwa, Ministry of Energy & Petroleum, Kenya
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Executive Summary

This research study builds on the Kenya 2023-2044 Least Cost Power Development Plan (LCPDP), with a special focus on emerging national and global issues. The Electric Cooking Technologies initiative is an integral part of Kenya's strategy to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and enhance climate change resilience, aligning with Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) 5 (Gender Equality) and 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy). It also supports Kenya's Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC) target of reducing carbon emissions by 32% by 2030. Further it is projected that E-cooking will influence power demand in the near future.

This report examines E cooking as a future demand driver with its analysis on generation mix, associated system cost and annual CO₂ emissions. Three forecast scenarios were developed based on projections of e-cooking demand. These scenarios are Reference, BAU and Full E-cooking forecast. Full E-Cooking Scenario envisions a complete transition to electric cooking by 2044, with 100% of total cooking demand met by electricity. Recommendations for capacity expansion with new capacity in resource are formulated based on the Full E-cooking forecast. Additionally, with E-Cooking Full Transition by 2044 higher investment costs will be incurred to meet the growing demand.

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1. Introduction

The power sector in Kenya is in a state of transition and is considered core in the Government's Energy Sector transition agenda. With the World currently consolidating its efforts towards climate change mitigation and building resilience towards negative impacts that come with it, Kenya is acutely attuned to the imperatives of this agenda and is fully demonstrating steadfast commitment to its realization.

Despite achieving an impressive electrification rate of 76.5% as of 2023, fueled largely by renewable sources, Kenya faces a glaring disconnect in the adoption of electric cooking. 3.9% of the population uses electricity as their primary fuel for cooking, while 61% still depend on polluting fuels like firewood and charcoal. These traditional cooking methods not only pose severe health risks but also contribute significantly to environmental degradation. Biomass fuels significantly contribute to Household Air Pollution (HAP) and major sources of Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions, and previous studies show that they account for up to 26.5% of Kenya's total GHG emission (GOK, 2020; Ministry of Energy & Petroleum, 2018; CCAK, 2019).

Transitioning to e-cooking in Kenya by 2044 raises significant research and policy queries, including how the adoption of e-cooking will influence Kenya's energy mix & demand, associated costs and what is the overall impact on greenhouse gas emissions will be with a full transition.

2. Methodology

OSeMOSYS is an open-source linear modeling system that can predict the optimal evolution of a country's energy matrix. The OSeMOSYS models the long-term analysis of the energy system due to its ability to minimize costs, comply with emission limits, and meet demand constraints. The Base SAND file for this work assignment was the 'Starter Kit' available at the Zenodo Repository. To calibrate the model, we updated the existing installed and planned capacities, energy generation history, reviewed the techno-economic data in the demand sectors demand for the years 2015-2022 using data from the annual national energy balance reports. Based on report provided by the LCPDP (The (draft) Kenya Least Cost Power Development Plan (LCPDP) Report 2023-2043.), three scenarios were evaluated with key research question: How will Kenya's electricity mix, demand projection, emissions, and overall systems costs evolve if the country were to mandate a full transition to e cooking by 2044?

Scenarios

1. **Business as Usual (BAU)**- Assumes a continuation of current trends without significant changes in policy or technology adoption.
2. **Reference Scenario** - Identifies cost-effective power generation projects while considering the gradual increase in electric cooking demand, with an annual potential demand growth of 4% by 2030 and 10% until the end of the planning period.
3. **Full E-cooking Scenario**- Envisions a complete transition to electric cooking, with 100% of total cooking demand met by electricity, year of full load expected to be in 2044.

Figure 1: Summary of scenarios explored in the modelling

- Data sources

1. The (draft) Kenya Least Cost Power Development Plan (LCPDP) Report 2023-2043.
2. Ministry of Energy and Petroleum commissioned the Kenya National e-Cooking Study (KNeCS) (Ministry of Energy & Petroleum, 2018)
3. Sustainable Energy for All Kenya Action Agenda. Kenya. <https://www.se4all-africa.org/seforall-in-africa/country-data/kenya/>
4. The (draft) Kenya electric Cooking Baseline Study (2023).

- Assumptions

- i. All domestic customers are expected to fully transition to e cooking by 2044.
- ii. Adequate grid electricity capacity, availability, and reliability.
- iii. E-cooking influences the growth in demand.
- iv. Special electricity tariffs during off peak.

3. Kenya Scenario Results

The graphs below show selected results for the three modelled scenarios, including yearly electricity generation and supply capacity, Residential Cooking Demand and total annual carbon dioxide emissions for 2021-2055.

3.1 Electricity Generation Results

As energy consumption increases across all scenarios, energy generation rises accordingly. Figure 2 shows the gradual increase in power generation, reaching approximately 620 PJ in the BAU scenario, 640 PJ in the REF scenario, and 720 PJ in the Full-ECKN scenario. The Full-ECKN scenario stands out due to its requirement to electrify the residential sector to meet the demand for E-cooking. Additionally, the results indicate that the country becomes energy independent, no longer needing to import electricity to meet its demand. The Full-ECKN scenario

also highlights the significant potential of biomass power generation, offering a more cost-effective energy solution for the residential sector.

Figure 2: Electricity Generation in the REF, BAU & FULL-ECKN scenarios for Kenya

3.2 Capacity Expansion Results

Figure 3: Installed capacity in the REF, BAU & FULL-ECKN scenarios for Kenya

Figure 3 shows there is a gradual increase in installed capacity to support the higher power generation needs. In the Full-ECKN scenario, the expansion of biomass power plant, will be pivotal in providing a cheaper energy solution for the residential sector specifically for E cooking demand. By increasing the installed capacity, the Full-ECKN scenario not only ensures that energy production meets rising consumption but also enhances the resilience and reliability of the energy supply system.

3.3 Residential Energy Production

Figure 4: Residential Cooking Demand for BAU, REF and FULL-ECKN Scenarios for Kenya

In the REF scenario, a complete transition to full E-cooking is projected to be achieved by 2070. However, with the government's ambitious targets, this transition is expected to be accomplished much earlier, by 2044, as illustrated in Figure 4.

3.4 Annual Carbon Dioxide Emissions Results

Figure 5: Annual Carbon Dioxide emissions in the BAU, REF and FULL-ECKN Scenarios for Kenya

The Full E-cooking scenario presents a significant reduction in CO2 emissions compared to the BAU and REF scenarios. However, towards the end of the planning period, there is an observed increase in emissions. This rise can likely be attributed to other sectors, including industry and transport.

3.5 Total Annual Costs

Figure 6: Total system costs 2021-2055.

Total costs encompass capital, fixed, and variable expenses associated with the development of the energy system. The estimated total costs for the BAU, REF, and Full E-cooking scenarios are US\$269 billion, US\$282 billion, and US\$368 billion, respectively. Achieving a full transition to meet residential electricity demand necessitates significantly higher investments compared to the BAU scenario, as illustrated in Figure 6.

4. Discussion

- Insights and results implications

Transitioning to full electric cooking significantly reduces CO₂ emissions compared to the BAU and REF scenarios, aiding climate change mitigation and helping to meet the country's SDG 5 and 7 goals as well as its NDC targets. Model results also show energy independence by eliminating the need for electricity imports in 2040. However, this transition necessitates a substantial increase in total costs, estimated at US\$368 billion versus US\$269 billion for the BAU scenario, and requires significant infrastructure development to support the increased residential electricity demand.

- Potential technologies/areas worth exploration/policy recommendations

Expanding renewable energy sources to meet increased electricity demand sustainably. Developing advanced energy storage technologies to manage the variability of renewables and ensure a reliable power supply for electric cooking; implementing smart grid technologies to enhance grid efficiency, and providing subsidies and incentives for households to transition to electric cooking appliances, thereby reducing the financial burden on consumers.

- Limitations of study

1. The study relies on certain assumptions and projections that may not fully capture future technological advancements or policy changes.

2. The primary focus on residential cooking may overlook emissions and energy consumption trends in other sectors like industry and transport.
3. The cost estimates may not account for all variables, such as unforeseen infrastructure costs or fluctuations in energy prices.
4. Limited data availability for some technologies could affect the accuracy of the results.

- Potential areas for future research (potential interventions and implementation challenges)

1. Investigating the impact of electrification on other sectors, such as industry and transport, to provide a holistic view of national emissions and energy use.
2. Analysing the effectiveness of different policy interventions, such as subsidies, tariffs, and regulations, in accelerating the transition to electric cooking.

5. Conclusion

This study highlights the significance of energy modeling in policy planning and the transition to sustainable energy systems, particularly within Kenya's energy landscape and its Least Cost Power Development Plan (LCPDP). This research demonstrates that transitioning to full electric cooking presents a viable pathway for reducing CO₂ emissions, aligning with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 5 and 7, and meeting the country's Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC) targets. Further, the model results emphasize the potential for achieving energy independence by eliminating the need for electricity imports. However, it is projected a substantial investment will be required for infrastructure development to support increased residential electricity cooking demand, as evidenced by the estimated total costs. Moving forward, exploring renewable energy integration, advanced energy storage solutions, smart grid technologies, and subsidies for electric cooking transitions emerge as key areas worth exploring and prioritizing in policy recommendations.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Acknowledgements

This section acknowledges the invaluable support and guidance received during the EMP-A 2024 capacity building event organized by the Climate Compatible Growth Programme (CCG). Special thanks to Fernando A. Plazas Niño, Pedro H. Peters Barbosa, Simone Osei-Owusu, and Pacifique KOSHIKWINJA Matabishi for their contributions.

Appendix B: Methodology

Detailed explanation of the methodology employed in the study, including the use of OSeMOSYS for energy modeling, data sources, assumptions made, and scenarios evaluated.

Appendix C: Data Sources

A list of primary data sources utilized in the study, including reports from the Ministry of Energy and Petroleum, Sustainable Energy for All, and other relevant sources.

Appendix D: Assumptions

This section outlines the key assumptions made during the modeling process, such as the full transition to electric cooking by 2044 and the availability of adequate grid electricity capacity.

Appendix E: Scenario Results

Comprehensive results from the three modeled scenarios (Business as Usual, Reference, and Full E-cooking), including graphs and data tables depicting electricity generation, capacity expansion, residential cooking demand, carbon dioxide emissions, and total annual costs.

Appendix F: Discussion

Additional insights, limitations of the study, potential areas for future research, and implications of the findings are elaborated in this section.

Appendix G: Figures

All figures referenced throughout the report are presented in this section for easy reference and review.

Appendix H: References

A list of all references cited in the report, including reports, studies, and other relevant literature.

